

STUDY OF THE WASTE OIL PURIFICATION PROCESS

M.B. Umarova¹, X.L. Pulatov²

Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology^{1,2}

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Abstract. In Uzbekistan, large-scale efforts are being undertaken to restore and purify used oils, improve their quality, and develop high-quality technical oils. During the use of motor, transformer, and industrial oils, they accumulate oxidation products, mechanical impurities, organic compounds, and other contaminants, which significantly reduce the quality of the oils. Used oils containing these pollutants cannot meet demand and must be replaced with fresh oils. However, collecting and regenerating used oils to preserve valuable oil resources is extremely cost-effective.

Keywords: emulsions, waste oil purifier, polyacrylates, resource-saving technologies.

Introduction. The regeneration of used oil can be carried out using a combination of physico-chemical, chemical, and physical processes. The composition of used oils should not exceed 4% of water, emulsions, and semi-liquid or liquid products. This requirement allows the regeneration process to proceed without the need for complex technologies. Worldwide, targeted research is being conducted to improve resource-saving technologies and equipment for the purification and regeneration of used oils. In this regard, it is important to develop an improved structural design for a waste oil purifier and implement an oil purification process that removes oxidation products in a resource-efficient manner. In our proposed scientific work, an improved schematic design of a laboratory device for oil purification using polyacrylates has been developed. As a result of tests, the proposed copolymers have been found to be highly effective in purifying used oils and are recommended as resource-efficient modifiers for waste oil purification based on synthesized copolymers.

Fig. 1. Process flow diagram of waste oil purification:

1,8 – Reactor, 2 – drum filter, 3,7 – pumps, 4 – distillation column, 5 – drum dryer, 6 – mixer, 9 – separator.

In the reactor (1), the prepared GAE copolymer is processed and then fed to the drum filter press (2), where the unreacted copolymer is separated from light volatile substances. The residue remaining on the filter is rinsed again using a small amount of filter drum equipment and then returned to the drum dryer for repeated filtration and drying.

After drying, the copolymer is directed to the mixing unit (6), where it is dissolved in benzene and pumped into the reactor (8) using pump (7) to enter into reaction. The heated oil undergoes the reaction at atmospheric pressure (1 atm) and a temperature of 70°C. The purified oil is then separated from the residue using a centrifuge-separator (9).

Infrared Spectroscopy of Mineral Oil

The IR spectroscopic method allows the identification of chemical changes in the sample. The FTIR (Fourier Transform Infrared) spectrometer used was a Japanese-made "SHIMADZU" spectrophotometer. The measurement range was 500–4000 cm⁻¹, with detection carried out using the Shedaga method at a resolution of 5 cm⁻¹. The spectra were obtained using the KBr pellet method (2 g of KBr and 9 mg of the sample). The average measurement error is ±5%.

IR spectrum of purified mineral oil

Atomic spectra consist of narrow lines, while molecular spectra consist of broad bands. The IR spectra of the obtained samples are presented graphically. The transmittance (T%) is plotted on the ordinate (Y-axis), and the wavenumber (cm⁻¹) — the number of waves per centimeter — is plotted on the abscissa (X-axis), representing the frequency of IR radiation incident on the sample.

Figure 2 shows the IR spectrograms of the purified mineral oil.

Fig. 2. A – Purified mineral oil; B – Unpurified mineral oil

The characteristic vibration frequencies of functional groups were identified based on the IR spectrum of the purified mineral oil shown in Figure 2.A. The IR spectrum is conventionally divided into regions corresponding to different types of bonds: double bonds (3500–2800 cm⁻¹), triple bonds (2300–2100 cm⁻¹), and another double bond region (1800–1540 cm⁻¹). These parts of the spectrum are specific to each substance. In both purified and unpurified oil, the stretching

vibrations of the OH group are observed in the range of 3440.03–3336.76 cm^{-1} , occurring between molecules, while intramolecular stretching vibrations are found in the range of 1160.83–1059.91 cm^{-1} [52, 103]. Tables present the characteristic vibration frequencies of functional groups obtained through both alkaline and acidic methods.

Table 1. Characteristic absorption regions of functional groups in the ir spectrum

Absorption Region (cm^{-1})	Group	Type of Vibration	Intensity
1738.97	–C–O–	Stretching (valence)	Strong
1458.04	–CH ₂	Asymmetric deformation	High
1373.75	(Nitrate ion) NO ₂	–	Strong
1230.22	–P–O–C–	Stretching (valence)	–
1165.42	–P–O–	Stretching (valence)	Strong
1028.54	–C–O–C–	Asymmetric stretching	Strong
726.54	Cyclobutane ring vibration	–	–

The functional vibrations of purified mineral oil are predominantly asymmetric stretching vibrations and are accompanied by strong intensity. The characteristic vibration frequencies of the functional groups in unpurified mineral oil are presented in Table 2. The functional vibrations of unpurified mineral oil are also mainly asymmetric in nature, and it can be observed that some functional group peaks are absent.

Thus, the difference in functional vibrations between purified and unpurified oils is significant. The intensity of the unpurified oil in the absorption spectroscopy is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Characteristic vibration frequencies of functional groups in unpurified oil

Absorption Region (cm^{-1})	Group	Type of Vibration	Intensity
1458.04	–CH ₂	Asymmetric deformation	High
1373.75	Nitrate ion (NO ₂)	–	Strong
726.54	Cyclobutane ring vibration	–	–

Figure 3. shows the graphical comparison of the IR spectra.

Fig. 3. Comparison of IR spectra of purified and unpurified mineral oils
Infrared Spectroscopy of ADDINOL Semi-Synthetic Oil

The IR spectroscopic method allows for the identification of chemical changes in the sample. The Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectrometer used was a Japanese "SHIMADZU"

spectrophotometer. The measurement range was 500–4000 cm^{-1} , with a detection resolution of 5 cm^{-1} . The spectra were obtained using the KBr pellet method (2 g of KBr and 9 mg of the sample). The average measurement error is $\pm 5\%$. The IR spectrum of the purified synthetic oil was obtained. Atomic spectra consist of sharp lines, while molecular spectra are represented by broad bands (or corridors). The IR spectra of the obtained samples are presented in graphical form. The transmittance (T%) is plotted along the Y-axis, while the X-axis shows the frequency of IR radiation incident on the sample (wavenumber – the number of waves per centimeter, expressed in cm^{-1}). The curvature of the graph reflects the relationship between these two values.

A – Purified synthetic oil

Fig. 4. IR spectrum of purified and unpurified ADDINOL semi-synthetic oil

Based on the IR spectrum of purified ADDINOL oil presented in Figure 4., the characteristic vibration frequencies of functional groups were identified. The reason why the entire IR spectrum is conventionally divided into the "two-bond region" (3500–2800 cm^{-1}), the "three-bond region" (2300–2100 cm^{-1}), the "double-bond region" (1800–1540 cm^{-1}), and the so-called "fingerprint region" is that these parts of the spectrum are specific to each substance. The characteristic vibration frequencies of functional groups observed in the IR spectra are presented in Table 1. In both purified and unrefined oil, the stretching vibrations of the C–O group range from 1738.97 to 726.54 cm^{-1} , occurring both between molecules and within the molecule itself.

Results of the IR analysis of unpurified oils.

Fig. 5. IR spectrum (general analysis) of unpurified oils

Table 3.

Wavenumber (cm^{-1})	Refined Functional Group Description
2929.83	–CH ₂ –
2855.00	–CH ₂ –

Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Refined Functional Group Description
1462.12	-CH ₃
1378.80	-CH ₃
1342.71	C(CH ₃) ₂
1111.12	C=C=O (functional group of ketene type)
1028.50	CH ₂ epoxide
1007.23	Cyclic CH ₂
1000.36	CH ₂ (in CH ₂ -CO type)
729.46	(CH ₂) _x repeating methylene chains
642.31	C-Hal (carbon-halogen bond)

Results of Comparative Analysis of the IR Spectra of Purified Oils

Fig. 6. IR spectrum (general analysis) of purified oils

Conclusion. The IR spectral analysis reveals the presence of various functional groups in the composition of unpurified oils. In particular, different functional groups were identified, such as CH₂ at 2929.83 cm⁻¹, CH₃ at 2855 cm⁻¹, C=C=O (a ketene-type functional group) at 1111.12 cm⁻¹, and carbon halides at 642.31 cm⁻¹. However, in the purified oils, a significant reduction in the presence of these functional groups was observed. This indicates the effective impact of the purification processes.

It was concluded that the purification performance showed better results in synthetic and semi-synthetic oils compared to mineral oils.

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